

Synthesis of Triaryl-*s*-triazines from 2,4,5-Triarylimidazoles in a Ring Expansion Reaction

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Manuscript received 27 April 1994, revised 21 October 1994, accepted 26 October 1994

The synthesis of *s*-triazines¹ and their pharmacological applications² are well documented. The *s*-triazine nucleus can be most readily synthesised by the trimerisation of nitriles² and also from pyrimidines³. Hence, we became interested to synthesise this class of compounds from the easily accessible 2-arylimidazoles, which in turn were obtained from diketones in a single pot reaction⁴.

Following the work of Hayasi *et al.*⁵, we became interested in producing the hydroperoxide intermediate in solution by bubbling oxygen into methanolic solution of 2,4,5-triphenylimidazole in presence of ammonium acetate, which could, in principle, interact with ammonium acetate to give the expected *s*-triazines. In a typical reaction, bubbling of a continuous stream of oxygen to a solution of 2,4,5-triphenylimidazole (**1a**) in methanol containing ammonium acetate for 4–5 h in fact yielded 61% of 2,4,6-triphenyl-*s*-triazine. Similarly, **1b-d** under identical reaction conditions afforded the corresponding *s*-triazines (**3b-d**) in 62% overall yield respectively (Scheme 1). In a similar manner, the imidazoles (**4a-d**) obtained from Entobex (Hindustan Ciba-Geigy) gave *s*-triazines (**6a-d**) in appreciable yields. Thus, we report herein a modified synthetic method for triaryl-*s*-triazines.

Experimental

The m.ps. were recorded in open capillaries on a Wiswo melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Thin layer chromatography were carried out using silica gel (ca. 0.2 mm; ACME Chemical). Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO-*d*₆ or CDCl₃)

Scheme 1

on a Perkin-Elmer 390 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Elemental analyses were carried out on a Heraeus CHN-O-RAPID instrument.

The 2,4,5-trisubstituted-imidazoles were synthesised according to the reported procedure⁴. These starting materials were used for further reactions after crystallisation.

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2,4,6-Trisubstituted-s-triazines. *General procedure* : To a stirred methanolic solution (20 ml) of 2,4,5-trisubstituted imidazole (**1a**; 0.6 g, 0.002 mol), purified oxygen from cylinder was bubbled continuously for 4–5 h at room temperature in the presence of ammonium acetate. The resulting solids were dried and crystallised from ether : **2,4,6-triphenyl-s-triazine (3a)**, yellow (61%), m.p. 234° (lit.⁶ 235°) (Found : C, 81.78; H, 5.03; N, 13.76. C₂₁H₁₅N₃ calcd. for : C, 81.55, H, 4.85; N, 13.59%); ν_{\max} 3 000, 1 610, 1 490 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃/DMSO-d₆) 7.15–7.45 (8H, m, ArH), 7.48–7.66 (5H, m, ArH), 8.03–8.21 (2H, m ArH); **2-(4-chlorophenyl)-4,6-diphenyl-s-triazine (3b)**, yellow (64%), m.p. 199° (Found : C, 73.63; H, 4.24; N, 12.43. C₂₁H₁₄N₃Cl calcd. for : C, 73.46; H, 4.08; N, 12.24%); ν_{\max} 3 050, 1 600, 1 400 cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-d₆) 7.18–7.57 (6H, m, ArH), 7.65–7.87 (6H, m, ArH), 7.91 (d, *J* 9 Hz, ArH); **2-(3-nitrophenyl)-4,6-diphenyl-s-triazine (3c)**, yellow (78%), m.p. 205° (Found : C, 71.34; H, 4.09; N, 16.03. C₂₁H₁₄N₄O₂ calcd. for : C, 71.18; H, 3.95; N, 15.81%); ν_{\max} 2 950, 1 610, 1 560 1 490 cm⁻¹; **2-(4-nitrophenyl)-4,6-diphenyl-s-triazine (3d)**, yellow (72%), m.p. 210° (Found : C, 71.29; H, 4.11; N, 15.98. C₂₁H₁₄N₄O₂ calcd. for : C, 71.18; H, 3.95; N, 15.81%); ν_{\max} 2 960, 1 600, 1 550, 1 500 cm⁻¹; **6a**, yellow (68%), m.p. 193° (Found : C, 73.72; H, 4.09; N, 22.74. C₁₉H₁₁N₅ calcd. for : C, 73.54; H, 3.87; N, 22.58%); ν_{\max} 2 975, 1 600 cm⁻¹; **6b**, yellowish red (62%), m.p. 212° (Found : C, 66.39; H, 3.34; N, 20.74. C₁₉H₁₀N₅Cl calcd. for : C, 66.28; H, 3.20; N, 20.34%); **6c**, yellow (67%), m.p. 155° (Found :

C, 64.52; H, 3.03; N, 23.79. C₁₉H₁₀N₆O₂ calcd. for : C, 64.40; H, 2.82; N, 23.66%); ν_{\max} 2 955, 1 600, 1 560, 1 500 cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-d₆) 7.49 (3H, br s, ArH), 8.03 (1H, s, ArH), 8.49–8.97 (4H, m, ArH), 9.06 (2H, br s, ArH); **6d**, yellowish red (54%), m.p. > 300° (Found : C, 64.54; H, 3.06; N, 23.83. C₁₉H₁₀N₆O₂ calcd. for : C, 64.40; H, 2.82; N, 23.66%); ν_{\max} 2 960, 1 600, 1 550, 1 500 cm⁻¹.

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance from U.G.C., New Delhi, is gratefully acknowledged.

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